

Impact of Teacher Qualifications and Teaching Materials on Social Studies Curriculum Implementation in Upper Basic Education in Delta State, Nigeria.

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Abstract

This study utilized a descriptive survey research design to investigate the impact of teacher qualifications, teaching materials availability, and their utilization on the effective implementation of the Social Studies curriculum in upper basic education level schools in Delta State, Nigeria. The research was conducted across three education zones—Delta Central, Delta North, and Delta South—targeting a population of 1,054 Social Studies teachers in government-owned schools. Using purposive sampling, 500 teachers were selected, and data were collected via a validated questionnaire titled ‘Implementation of UBELS Social Studies Curriculum Questionnaire (IUBELSSSCQ).’ The instrument’s reliability coefficient was determined to be 0.72. Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics, including Pearson Product Moment Correlation. Findings showed a moderate positive relationship between teacher qualifications and curriculum implementation effectiveness, underscoring the importance of qualified teachers. Additionally, while textbooks were widely available, the average availability of other recommended teaching materials was 40%, indicating limited resources. The study also found a significant relationship between the availability and utilization of teaching materials and curriculum implementation effectiveness. The study concludes that both qualified teaching staff and adequate resources are essential for effective curriculum implementation. Recommendations include enhancing teacher training, increasing material access, encouraging strategic resource utilization, and integrating technology to support instructional practices.

Keywords: Teacher qualifications, teaching materials, curriculum implementation, Social Studies, Upper Basic Education

Introduction

The implementation of a curriculum is pivotal to achieving educational objectives, and effective teaching and learning depend on how well curriculum guidelines are followed (Batubara et.al, 2023). Social Studies, designed as a transformative subject in Nigeria, was introduced to address the societal challenges left unaddressed by traditional disciplines like Geography, History, and Civics (Sunday et.al, 2020)

The subject aims to instill societal norms, values, and behaviors necessary for harmonious living and responsible citizenship. However, despite its introduction over four decades ago, Nigeria continues to face high levels of social issues, including youth restiveness, corruption, examination malpractice, and other forms of social deviance (Babatunde et.al, 2022).

This gap between educational aims and societal outcomes raises concerns about the implementation of Social Studies at the upper basic level, especially concerning the role of teacher qualification, availability of teaching materials, and effective utilization of these resources.

The effective implementation of the Social Studies curriculum in upper basic education (Junior Secondary School levels) in Delta State faces significant challenges. Qualified teachers, adequate teaching resources, and professional development are essential for achieving curriculum objectives. Teachers who lack proper training in Social Studies education may struggle with curriculum interpretation and delivery, leading to ineffective teaching practices and suboptimal learning outcomes (Amalu et.al, 2023). Furthermore, limited availability and inadequate utilization of instructional materials hinder teachers' ability to deliver experiential and engaging lessons, forcing many to revert to lecture-based teaching methods (Chigbu & Adamu, 2023). Therefore, there is a need to explore the extent of teacher qualification, availability and utilization of teaching materials, and the role of professional development in strengthening Social Studies education in Delta State.

Teachers are central to the effective implementation of any curriculum, as they mediate the delivery of curriculum content in classrooms. According to Ssempala and Namazzi (2024) curriculum implementation involves teachers' adherence to instructional guidelines, planning, and evaluation methods prescribed in curriculum documents. Teachers' qualifications significantly impact their ability to interpret, plan, and deliver Social Studies lessons that foster societal values, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills (Wiens et.al, 2022). Unqualified teachers, however, often lack the expertise required to deliver the curriculum effectively, which compromises the quality of education received by students. Professional development programmes aimed at equipping Social Studies teachers with relevant skills and knowledge are thus vital in promoting effective curriculum implementation.

Instructional materials are essential in making Social Studies relatable and engaging for students, yet studies reveal a persistent scarcity of such resources across Nigerian schools (Chigbu et.al, 2023). Even when available, these resources are underutilized, leading to over-reliance on traditional "chalk and talk" methods, which limit students' exposure to interactive and practical learning experiences. Studies by Zengulaaru and Nyamekye (2023) found out that the inadequacy of instructional materials contributes significantly to the ineffectiveness of Social Studies teaching. They also claimed that there is often a disparity in the availability of these materials between urban and rural schools, a situation which compounds the challenges of curriculum implementation in less-resourced areas.

The study by Ikpeme et.al (2021) explores the positive impact of teachers' quality on students' academic performance in public primary schools in Calabar, Nigeria, showing a significant correlation between effective teaching practices and improved student outcomes, and recommending a supportive, stress-free classroom environment. This study by Ibrahim (2018) evaluated the impact of teachers' experience and qualifications on the implementation of the Junior Secondary School Social Studies curriculum in Kaduna State, Nigeria, revealing that while gender had no significant effect, differences in qualification significantly impacted curriculum implementation, recommending that teachers stay updated with relevant innovations.

Ezene (2022) study examined how teachers' qualifications, gender, and use of instructional materials affect Social Studies performance among Upper Basic students in Delta State, finding that each factor significantly impacts student performance and recommending that only qualified Social Studies teachers be deployed to enhance academic outcomes. Edinyang et al. (2017) explored the relationship between instructional materials, teachers' attitudes, and the implementation of the Social Studies curriculum for effective citizenship in Cross River State, Nigeria. They found that both resources and teacher attitudes significantly impacted curriculum implementation and recommended that teachers remain informed about new developments in civic and citizenship education.

Statement of Problem

The persistent gap between the intended outcomes of the Social Studies curriculum in Nigeria and the current state of societal values and behaviors, such as youth restiveness, corruption, and social deviance, raises critical concerns about the effectiveness of curriculum implementation at the upper basic education level, particularly in Delta State. Despite the aim of Social Studies to foster societal norms, values, and responsible citizenship, the subject has not achieved its transformative potential. The primary issues hindering effective curriculum implementation include the qualifications of teachers, the availability of instructional materials, and professional development opportunities for educators.

Teachers' qualifications and expertise in Social Studies are crucial for effective curriculum delivery, yet many teachers lack the necessary training to interpret and implement the curriculum effectively. This deficiency leads to inconsistent teaching practices that hinder the cultivation of critical thinking, problem-solving skills, and societal values among students. Inadequate instructional materials further exacerbate this issue, as the scarcity of resources limits teachers' ability to deliver interactive and experiential learning experiences, often resulting in a reliance on traditional lecture-based methods. This situation is particularly dire in rural schools, where resource allocation is even more limited, widening the gap in educational quality.

Additionally, the absence of continuous professional development (CPD) for Social Studies teachers prevents them from staying updated with modern pedagogical approaches and limits their capacity to address emerging educational challenges effectively. Without ongoing CPD programmes, teachers struggle to utilize available instructional materials effectively or to adopt innovative teaching strategies that could make Social Studies more engaging and impactful for students.

Therefore, this study aims to examine the influence of teacher qualifications, availability and utilization of instructional materials, and professional development on the implementation of the Social Studies curriculum in Delta State's upper basic education level.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

1. How qualified are the teachers involved in the implementation of upper basic education level schools' Social Studies curriculum in Delta State?
2. To what extent are recommended teaching materials available for the implementation of upper basic education level schools' Social Studies curriculum in Delta State.
3. To what extent are recommended teaching materials utilized in the implementation of upper basic level Social Studies curriculum in Delta State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide the study and tested at 0.05 level of significance for the study:

H0₁: There is no significant relationship between teachers' qualifications and the effective implementation of the Social Studies curriculum in upper basic education level schools in Delta State.

H0₂: There is no significant relationship between the availability of recommended teaching materials and the implementation of the Social Studies curriculum in upper basic education level schools in Delta State.

H0₃: There is no significant relationship between the utilization of recommended teaching materials and the effective implementation of the Social Studies curriculum in upper basic education level schools in Delta State

Method

The study adopted the descriptive survey research design. The study was conducted in the three education zones of Delta State which include; Delta Central, Delta North and Delta South. Population of the study was 1,054 upper basic education level schools' Social Studies teachers in government owned secondary schools in Delta State. Purposive sampling was used and all the 500 Social Studies teachers in upper basic education level schools in Delta State were all used for the study. For the purpose of gathering data from the sampled respondents in this study, a researcher-designed questionnaire titled 'implementation of UBELS Social Studies Curriculum Questionnaire (IUBELSSCQ)' was used. The instrument was validated by three experts, two in Social Studies and one expert in measurement and evaluation all from the Delta State University, Abraka. To determine the reliability of the instrument, the instrument was administered to 40 Social Studies teachers in private owned upper basic education level schools in Delta State. A test interval of two weeks was allowed between the administrations of the instrument. Scores from the administrations were correlated using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation statistics. The reliability coefficient was found to be 0.72 and it was accepted. Research questions were answered using percentages, mean and standard deviation while hypotheses were analyzed with Pearson Product Moment Correlation statistics.

Research Question One

How qualified are the teachers involved in the implementation of upper basic education level schools' Social Studies curriculum in Delta State?

The summary of the analyzed data has been presented in table 1 below.

Table 1: Qualification of Social Studies Teachers Sampled in Delta State

Qualification	N	%
M.ED	83	16.7
B.ED	283	56.6
HND	34	6.7
NCE	100	20.0
Total	500	100

Source: Field work

Table 1 presents the qualifications of the sampled social studies teachers used for the study. Out of the 100 respondents, 15 hold Masters (M.ED) degree which represents 16.7%; 61 hold Bachelors (B.Ed) degree which represents 56.6%; 6 hold Higher National Diploma (HND) which represent 6.7% while 18 hold Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE) which represents 20% of the sample. Given that the mode falls within the B.Ed class, the researcher concluded that the social studies teachers involved in the implementation of upper basic education level schools’ Social Studies curriculum in Delta State are qualified. Only 18 representing 26% had a lower qualification other than the B.Ed.

Research Question Two

To what extent are recommended teaching materials available for the implementation of upper basic education level schools’ Social Studies curriculum in Delta State. The result of the data analysis has been summarized in the table 2 below.

Table 2: Availability of Recommended Teaching Materials

S/N	Instructional Material	No. Available	% Availability
1	Textbook	90	100
2	Video	9	10
3	Pictures	75	83
4	Charts	75	83
5	Posters	54	60
6	Documentaries	18	20
7	Motion pictures	6	7
8	Cultural regalia	36	40
9	Role cards	45	50
10	Road Safety guidelines	24	27
11	Newspaper	63	70
12	Magazine	48	53
13	Radio	18	20
14	Television	9	10
15	Cartoons	21	23
16	Simulation Games	21	23
17	NAFDAC posters	18	20
18	NDLEA posters	15	17
19	Dictionary	84	93
20	EFCC posters	9	10
21	Family tree	72	80
22	Film trips	6	7
23	The Nigerian Constitution	51	57
24	Artifacts	27	30
25	Photographs	54	60
26	Local Agreement on Human Right	21	23
27	Axe	24	27
28	Int’l Agreement on Human Right	18	20
	Average Availability %		40%

Table 2 showed the number of availability of teaching materials in the sampled schools. It shows that only textbooks are available in all the schools sampled. 84 respondents indicated the presence of a dictionary while pictures and charts are 75 each representing 83%. Family tree was 72 representing 80% while newspaper was 63 representing 70%. Other materials available included posters and photographs with 54 in numbers, the Nigerian Constitution 51 in number, magazine 48 and role cards 45 representing 60%, 57%, 53% and 50% respectively. Others included cultural regalia-36, artifacts-27, road safety guidelines and axe-24 each, cartoons, simulation games, Local agreement on human rights-21 each while others are 6 and below, the lowest being motion picture and film trips with 6 each representing 7% each. The average percentage (%) availability of these teaching materials was 40%. Based on the analysis above, the researcher concluded that the recommended teaching materials are available to a very low extent. Classroom interaction is typically based on textbooks, pictures, charts, posters, dictionary, photographs and family tree. Others are used sparingly in a school where they exist.

Research Question Three

To what extent are recommended teaching materials utilized in the implementation of upper basic education level schools' Social Studies curriculum in Delta State?

The result of the data analysis has been summarized in table 3 below.

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of Teaching Material Utilization

Variable	N	\bar{X}	SD
Teaching Material Utilization	90	58.03	30.9

Table 3 presented the summary of mean and standard deviation on the extent the recommended teaching materials are utilized. The mean (\bar{X}) utilization of the sample was 58.03 while the standard deviation was 30.9. A low mean and a high standard deviation denotes that the utilization of the teaching materials in upper basic education level schools' Social Studies study is on the average. The researcher therefore concluded that teaching materials utilization is not high neither is it too low in upper basic education level schools' Social Studies classes in Delta State.

Hypothesis One

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between teachers' qualifications and the effective implementation of the Social Studies curriculum in upper basic education level schools in Delta State.

Table 4: Summary of data and Pearson product moment correlation between teachers' qualifications and the effective implementation of the Social Studies curriculum in upper basic education level schools in Delta State.

Variable	N	Mean	STD.D	DF	R	P-Value	Remark
Teacher qualification	500	16.21	4.053	604	0.405		
Effective implementation of SOS curriculum	500	17.31	2.093			0.000*	Sig.

* denotes significant relationship at 0.05 level of significant

Table 4 is Correlation between Teachers' Qualifications and Effective Implementation of the Social Studies Curriculum. The result shows that there is a positive and moderate significant relationship between the independent variable (teachers' qualifications) and the dependent variable (effective implementation of the Social Studies curriculum) ($r = 0.405$, $df = 604$, $P < 0.05$). Since the P-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis that stated that there is no significant relationship between teachers' qualifications and the effectiveness of Social Studies curriculum implementation is rejected. Hence, there is a significant relationship between teachers' qualifications and the effectiveness of Social Studies curriculum implementation

Hypothesis Two

H0₂: There is no significant relationship between the availability of recommended teaching materials and the implementation of the Social Studies curriculum in upper basic education level schools in Delta State.

Table 5: Summary of data and Pearson product moment correlation between the availability of recommended teaching materials and the implementation of the Social Studies curriculum in upper basic education level schools in Delta State.

Variable	N	Mean	STD.D	DF	R	P-Value	Remark
Teacher qualification	500	16.39	2.224	604	0.520		
Availability of recommended teaching materials	500	17.31	2.093			0.000*	Sig.

* denotes significant relationship at 0.05 level of significant

Table 5 is Correlation between the Availability of Recommended Teaching Materials and Effective Implementation of the Social Studies Curriculum. The result shows that there is a positive and moderate significant relationship between the independent variable (availability of recommended teaching materials) and the dependent variable (effective implementation of the Social Studies curriculum) ($r = 0.520$, $df = 604$, $P < 0.05$). Since the P-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected, therefore there is a significant relationship between the availability of recommended teaching materials and the implementation of the Social Studies curriculum.

Hypothesis Three

H0₃: There is no significant relationship between the utilization of recommended teaching materials and the effective implementation of the Social Studies curriculum in upper basic education level schools in Delta State

Table 6: Summary of data and Pearson product moment correlation between the utilization of recommended teaching materials and the effective implementation of the Social Studies curriculum in upper basic education level schools in Delta State

Variable	N	Mean	STD.D	DF	R	P-Value	Remark
Teacher qualification	500	15.43	4.073	604	0.606	0.000*	Sig.
Utilization of recommended teaching materials	500	17.31	2.093				

* denotes significant relationship at 0.05 level of significant

Table 6 is Correlation between the Utilization of Recommended Teaching Materials and Effective Implementation of the Social Studies Curriculum. The result indicates that there is a positive and strong significant relationship between the independent variable (utilization of recommended teaching materials) and the dependent variable (effective implementation of the Social Studies curriculum) ($r = 0.606$, $df = 604$, $P < 0.05$). Since the P-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected which means that there is a significant relationship between the utilization of recommended teaching materials and the implementation of the Social Studies curriculum.

Discussion of Findings

The result of the analysis in table 4 revealed a moderate positive correlation between teachers' qualifications and the effective implementation of the Social Studies curriculum ($r = 0.405$, $df = 604$, $P < 0.05$). This result suggests that higher teacher qualifications contribute to better implementation of the curriculum, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Scholars highlight the importance of teacher qualifications for educational quality and curriculum effectiveness. This finding is corroborated by Darling-Hammond et.al (2024) who asserted that teacher qualifications, including subject-specific expertise and pedagogical skills, are crucial for fostering meaningful learning environments and for the successful implementation of curricular goals. In the same vein, Ugbede (2024) found that teachers with higher educational credentials are better equipped to interpret and deliver curriculum content, thereby enhancing students' comprehension and engagement. In this context, the findings align with the perspective that qualified teachers possess the requisite knowledge and skills to adapt the curriculum effectively to meet students' needs. Such educators are more likely to employ diverse instructional strategies that can make the Social Studies curriculum more impactful and engaging for students, a view supported by Ikpeeme et.al (2021) who links teacher effectiveness to curriculum mastery and pedagogical versatility.

Results from Table 5 indicated a moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.520$, $df = 604$, $P < 0.05$) between the availability of recommended teaching materials and the effective implementation of the Social Studies curriculum. This finding implies that schools with greater access to recommended materials experience a more effective curriculum implementation. This finding is

in agreement with Isola et.al (2021) who emphasize that adequate resources enable teachers to illustrate concepts more clearly, facilitating students' comprehension and retention.

Moreover, Edinyang et.al (2017) found that educational materials enhance teaching effectiveness by providing concrete examples and fostering interactive learning experiences. The availability of recommended materials thus enables teachers to deliver lessons more dynamically, supporting students in grasping Social Studies concepts more thoroughly. This is consistent with the findings of Wen (2021) which posited that materials stimulate learners' cognitive engagement and promote deeper understanding, as they provide tangible tools for exploring abstract ideas.

The correlation analysis in Table 6 showed a strong positive relationship between the utilization of recommended teaching materials and effective curriculum implementation ($r = 0.606$, $df = 604$, $P < 0.05$). This strong correlation indicates that the more effectively teachers utilize the materials at their disposal, the better the implementation of the curriculum. This result aligns with studies that stress not only the importance of material availability but also their effective application in teaching practices. This finding is supported by Offem et.al (2018) who argued that merely having resources is insufficient if they are not actively and thoughtfully used in classroom instruction.

Scholars like Irasuti et.al (2024) and Ezene (2022) underscored the need for effective utilization of teaching materials can enhance instructional clarity and foster student engagement. In their view Xi et.al (2021) revealed that effective use of recommended materials allows teachers to structure lessons in a way that builds on students' prior knowledge noting that scaffolding learning in line with social constructivist approach. According to them, this approach encourages active participation and ensures that students construct knowledge through guided discovery, significantly enriching their Social Studies learning experiences.

Conclusion

This study underscores the essential role of teacher qualifications and resource availability in the effective implementation of the Social Studies curriculum. Findings reveal a moderate positive correlation between teachers' qualifications and curriculum effectiveness, highlighting that teachers with higher qualifications are better equipped to implement the curriculum in ways that enhance student engagement and comprehension. Additionally, access to recommended teaching materials and their effective utilization were shown to significantly impact curriculum implementation. Schools with adequate resources not only experience more effective curriculum delivery, but teachers also leverage these materials to foster interactive, engaging learning experiences. Collectively, these findings emphasize that a qualified teaching workforce and access to well-utilized instructional materials are vital components for achieving impactful Social Studies education.

Recommendations

The following recommendation are made from the study:

1. Educational institutions and policymakers should provide ongoing professional development that enhances subject-specific knowledge and pedagogical skills for Social Studies teachers to improve curriculum implementation and student outcomes.
2. Schools should maintain a steady supply of recommended Social Studies resources, and educational authorities should allocate sufficient funding, especially in underserved regions, to support effective curriculum delivery.

3. Teacher training programmes should focus on the strategic integration of instructional materials into classroom practices.
4. Schools and institutions should organize workshops and seminars to train teachers on effectively incorporating available resources into lesson plans to foster active and interactive learning.
5. Schools should promote collaborative teaching, enabling educators to share resources, strategies, and best practices, and consider forming professional learning communities to collectively improve instructional methods.
6. Schools should prioritize integrating technology in Social Studies, enhancing resource availability and providing access to various digital tools for teaching.

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